

Compound D (gramine) was crystallised from acetone as colourless needles (60 mg), m.p. 134°; perchlorate, m.p. 150-151°; identified^{1,5} by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

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An Efficient Method for Estimation of Trace Level Mercury in Chlor-alkali Effluents

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THE high toxicity of mercury and its presence in many unsuspected sources have prompted many workers to recommend methods to eliminate the sources of its contamination or to reduce its content maximally. In recent years there has been considerable interest for developing better methods for the removal of mercury from aqueous solutions. Every method suffers from one or the other drawback. We now report an efficient method of removal of

chloride, followed by the separation and determination of mercury at trace level by extraction with ethylacetate. The suitability of the method for the removal of mercury from effluent samples of chlor-alkali industry has been verified.

Experimental

Materials: A stock solution (mg ml^{-1}) of mercuric chloride was prepared and diluted appropriately. The tracer ^{203}Hg in the form of solution of mercuric nitrate in nitric acid was supplied by B.A.R.C., Bombay. Ethylacetate was used after purification by distillation. All other chemicals used were sufficiently pure.

Effluent samples from a chlor-alkali industry situated in Andhra Pradesh, were collected from different spots. Care was taken not to introduce excessive air into the samples.

Equipment: An E.C.I.L. S.C. 604 single channel analyser coupled with a 3" well type scintillation detector and an E.C.I.L. M.A. 5800A mercury analyser were used.

Procedure for extraction of mercury: 15 ml of the aqueous phase containing 45000 counts for 50 ml^{-1} of mercury tracer and appropriate concentrations of mercury at 35° was extracted briskly for 5 min with an equal volume of ethylacetate in a 60 ml separatory funnel. After allowing for 10 min the layers were separated and analysed using scintillation counter.

Procedure for the estimation of mercury in effluents: The pH of the effluent was adjusted to 2-3 and the chloride content in the sample was initially determined by potentiometric titration using silver nitrate. Stoichiometric amounts of the solution of lead acetate (20%) containing glacial acetic acid (1%) and sodium fluoride (1%) solutions were added to the effluent and stirred well. The resultant precipitate (PbCl_2) was allowed to digest on a water bath for 1 h. The precipitate was filtered through a sintered glass crucible, washed several times with saturated lead acetate solution and water. The filtrate was transferred into a 250 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with water. Mercury was extracted with ethylacetate¹ and its content assayed.

Results and Discussion

The mechanism of the extraction of mercury from aqueous solutions with ethylacetate is through the formation of a solvated species of the type $\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{S}$ ($\text{S} = \text{ethylacetate}^{1,2}$). Using the standard procedure for the extraction¹, the pertinent variables such as pH, chloride concentration and extractant, were studied and the optimum conditions for the extraction were determined.

The results on the study of interferences show that the tolerance of diverse ions is fairly good. Since chloride is a serious interference in the

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TABLE 1—ADSORPTION OF MERCURY ON PbClF

Chloride mg ml ⁻¹	Total vol. of solution = 10 ml	
	Mercury μg ml ⁻¹	% Adsorption on 1 g of PbClF
5.55	1.00	3.80
7.40	1.00	7.00
11.10	1.00	12.50
14.80	1.00	15.00
22.20	1.00	15.10
7.40	5.00	6.00
7.40	12.50	2.10
7.40	15.00	1.00
7.40	20.00	0.45
7.40	25.00	0.38

and attained a minimum value of 0.5, which is negligible. This clearly shows that in the precipitation of chloride as PbClF in the presence of mercury (20 μg ml⁻¹) from chloride solutions (7.5 mg ml⁻¹), the loss of mercury due to adsorption is negligible. Therefore, in order to avoid interference of chloride in the extraction of mercury by ethylacetate, precipitation of chloride as PbClF was carried out prior to the extraction step. The results of the analysis of the samples, synthetic and those obtained from the chlor alkali industry, are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ANALYSIS OF SAMPLES

Sample	[Hg ²⁺] taken μg ml ⁻¹	Directed method [Hg ²⁺] found Mercury analyser	Extraction method [Hg ²⁺] recovered	
			Mercury analyser	Substoichiometric
Synthetic	5.0	5.0 ± 0.006	4.987 ± 0.026	4.962 ± 0.026
Synthetic	10.0	9.991 ± 0.024	9.980 ± 0.004	9.998 ± 0.011
Synthetic	20.0	19.995 ± 0.015	19.968 ± 0.002	20.017 ± 0.009
Synthetic Effluent	25.0	23.013 ± 0.004	25.047 ± 0.005	25.020 ± 0.008
Sample 1 (at point of emission)	—	18.802 ± 0.007	18.750 ± 0.024	18.847 ± 0.021
Sample 2 (at 2 m down stream)	—	15.447 ± 0.021	15.501 ± 0.016	15.497 ± 0.005
Sample 3 (at 10 m down stream)	—	1.500 ± 0.001	1.479 ± 0.003	1.600 ± 0.012

extraction of mercury, removal of chloride from sample solutions prior to extraction is necessary. Removal of chloride in presence of mercury by precipitation as silver chloride resulted in the loss of 20-25% of mercury, due to the adsorption of mercury on the precipitate. Further, the precipitate is not easily filterable even after digestion for a long time. On the other hand, the adsorption of mercury on lead chlorofluoride under suitable conditions is negligible. Hence, the precipitation of PbClF, a procedure^{3,4} usually chemists use to estimate fluoride content in rocks, has been made use of in the removal of chloride prior to the extraction step. Experiments were conducted using ²⁰³Hg tracer to study the adsorption of mercury at trace level on the precipitate, PbClF, as a function of chloride and mercury concentrations in the solutions (Table 1). From the results it can be seen that with the variation of chloride in solution, the percent-adsorption of mercury on PbClF increased upto a limiting value, 15. On the other hand, the variation of mercury concentration at a fixed chloride concentration in solution, the percent-adsorption decreased gradually with the increase of mercury concentration

The proposed method is selective for the separation of trace amounts of mercury from chloride solutions (0.1M). The advantage of the proposed method lies in the use of ethylacetate as extractant for the separation of mercury. Ethylacetate is a readily available solvent at a low cost compared to other high molecular weight amines^{5,6}.

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